

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Research in progress

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Gregory, K., Ninkov, A., Ripp, C., Peters, I., & Haustein, S. (2022). Surveying practices of data citation and reuse across disciplines. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators, STI 2022* (sti22105).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6951437>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Surveying practices of data citation and reuse across disciplines

Kathleen Gregory^{*}, Anton Ninkov^{*}, Chantal Ripp^{*,**}, Isabella Peters^{***} and Stefanie Haustein^{*,****}

^{*}*kathleen.gregory@uottawa.ca; aninkov@uottawa.ca; stefanie.haustein@uottawa.ca*

School of Information Studies and Scholarly Communications Lab, University of Ottawa, 55 Laurier Ave East, Ottawa, K1N 6N5 (Canada)

^{**}*chantal.ripp@uottawa.ca*

Library, University of Ottawa, 65 University Private, Ottawa, K1N 6N5 (Canada)

^{***}*i.peters@zbw.eu*

ZBW - Leibniz Information Center for Economics & Kiel University, Duesternbrooker Weg 120, 24105 Kiel (Germany)

^{****}

Observatoire des Sciences et des Technologies (OST), Centre Interuniversitaire de Recherche sur la Science et la Technologie (CIRST), Université du Québec à Montréal, CP 8888, Succ. Centre-Ville, Montreal, H3C 3P8.

Introduction

Understanding data citation and reuse in context is difficult. Infrastructures, practices, and the disciplinary metadata needed to put data citations in context are often unstandardized or nonexistent (Robinson-Garcia et al., 2016; Ninkov et al., 2021). While many researchers do not cite data formally, they do acknowledge them informally within the body of academic papers (Park et al., 2018). Little is known, however, about researchers' motivations for referencing and citing data (Silvello, 2018).

While the development of data metrics could incentivize data sharing and reuse (Lowenberg et al., 2019), the lack of knowledge about how researchers cite data makes it difficult to trace data practices and develop meaningful indicators. More evidence is needed to better understand data reuse, an important antecedent of data citation.

Surveys can shed light on researchers' motivations for citing (or not citing) data and help to situate practices in disciplinary contexts. Tenopir et al. (2020) found that perceptions of data sharing vary significantly by discipline, although they make no claims as to representivity. Schmidt et al. (2016) controlled for disciplinary differences using a two-sample comparison approach. Gregory et al. (2020) conducted separate analyses for researchers identifying with one versus multiple disciplinary domains. Despite the importance of disciplinary norms, none of these surveys attempted to create a representative sample based on academic discipline.

This research-in-progress paper describes preliminary results of a representative survey of academic authors by disciplines, with 2,492 complete responses, which investigates how and

why researchers cite and reuse data. Here, we describe our sampling methodology to detail how we address disciplinary representativity and provide initial descriptive statistics.

Methods

Questionnaire development

The questionnaire (Gregory et al., 2022) had two main branches questioning respondents who have reused data and those who have not. We used two rounds of review to improve the questionnaire's understandability and accuracy, one with experts and one with 1,000 pilot-researchers. The pilot study yielded a 1.2% response rate; pilot study responses are not included in our results below.

Sampling and recruitment

Our population of interest consisted of corresponding authors on papers indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) between 2016 and 2020; we aimed to create a representative sample by discipline of this population.

Step one: Creating a stratified random sample by discipline

First, we determined the percentage of academic authors by discipline in the overall population, using the Observatoire des Sciences et des Technologies (OST) local WoS database. We queried this database for articles published in the last five years. Each retrieved article had an associated email address for the corresponding author and a journal-level subject classification assignment. This resulted in 8.2 million articles and 5.8 million unique email addresses.

To facilitate comparison with DataCite, we mapped the National Science Foundation subject codes used in the OST database to the OECD's revised Field of Science and Technology (FOS) classification (OECD, 2007). The FOS schema, with six high-level fields and 42 sub-categories, provides a balance between breadth and specificity. The subject distributions for the six high-level FOS fields for email addresses and articles closely mirrored each other, with the exception of the humanities. To avoid under-sampling humanities researchers, we used the subject distribution of *articles* as the basis for sampling (see Table 1).

Using this distribution, we determined the number of participants to recruit from each discipline to achieve a confidence interval of 0.025. We randomly sampled unique emails accordingly.

Step two: Recruitment; participant classification; disciplinary mapping

A total of 158,600 recruitment emails were sent between 18 January and 4 March using SurveyMonkey. One reminder email was sent after two weeks.

Classifying researchers via journal-level subject classifications can be problematic. We therefore allowed participants to also select their own FOS sub-discipline. After three weeks, we mapped participants' selected disciplines to the high-level FOS fields and compared this to our desired sampling distributions (Table 1). We also recruited another 5,000 participants from Medical and Health Sciences. Data collection stopped once the desired percentages in *all* fields were met.

Table 1. Summary and comparison of disciplinary classification approaches

OECD class	Minimum sample size	Responses based on journal classification	Responses based on participant classification	Percentage of minimum sample	Change between journal and participant classification	Desired percentage of sample
Natural Sciences	597	990	1037	174%	47 (4.75%)	38.9%
Engineering and Technology	259	247	319	124%	72 (29.2%)	16.9%
Medical and Health Sciences	450	660	488	109%	-172 (26.1%)	29.3%
Agricultural Sciences	51	95	106	208%	11 (11.6%)	3.3%
Social Sciences	137	411	463	338%	52 (12.7%)	8.9%
Humanities	42	106	96	229%	-10 (9.4%)	2.7%
Total	1536	2509	2509	163%	364(14.5%)	100.0%

As seen in Table 1, using a journal-level subject classification as a proxy for disciplinary expertise was most effective in the natural sciences, which had the least difference between the participant-selected and journal-based classifications. The method was less effective in, i.e. engineering and technology.

Preliminary findings

We received 2,509 complete responses, as seen in Table 1. During data cleaning, we identified and removed 17 respondents whose responses had been incorrectly recorded by the survey system. This yielded 2,492 complete responses and an uncorrected response rate of 1.57%. Controlling for invalid emails, bounced emails and opt-outs (n=5,201) produced a response rate of 1.62%, similar to surveys using similar recruitment methods (Gregory et al., 2020). The completion rate was 68.6%; 3,632 individuals clicked through to the first page.

Figure 1 presents respondents' disciplines, geographic distribution, career stage, and employment organizations (n=2,492). The majority of respondents are in middle to senior career stages, reflecting our recruitment strategy targeting corresponding authors. Universities, followed by research institutions, are respondents' principal places of employment. Approximately two-thirds of respondents self-identify as men (65%) and one-third as women (32%), with a more balanced gender distribution in medical and health, social sciences, and the humanities.

Figure 1. Demographic characteristics of respondents (n=2,492).

The majority of respondents report reusing data (81.3%) and sharing their own data (80.5%). This indicates a potential self-selection bias in our sample towards people who share and reuse data. Interestingly, across disciplines, there is a tendency to reuse *both* quantitative and qualitative data more than either data type alone. The exception to this trend is in the social sciences, where 60.4% report solely reusing quantitative data.

The majority of respondents who reuse data indicate that they cite data by including a data citation in a reference list (69.4%); 23.1% sometimes do so. This contradicts past bibliometric research demonstrating an overall lack of formal data citations (Ninkov et al., 2021; Peters et al., 2016), but is perhaps reflective of the fact that respondents are primarily data reusers.

Respondents who indicated citing data in reference lists were asked about their motivations for doing so (Figure 2). Intrinsic motivations, i.e. as a way to show intellectual debt, to assist others in locating data, and to support the validity of claims, were selected more frequently than external reasons. Less than 10% state that they cite data because they were advised to by journals.

Figure 2. Why do you cite data? Multiple responses possible (n=1876).

Discussion

Here, we detailed a two-tier methodology for creating a representative sample of academic authors by disciplines. We further presented preliminary insights into data reuse and citation practices of researchers; this will be expanded in future work examining differences between disciplines.

References

- Gregory, K., Groth, P., Scharnhorst, A., & Wyatt, S. (2020). Lost or found? Discovering data needed for research. *Harvard Data Science Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.e38165eb>
- Gregory, K., Ninkov, A., Peters, I., Haustein, S. (2022). Questionnaire: A survey on data citation and reuse practices. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6505207>
- Lowenberg, D., Chodacki, J., Fenner, M., Kemp, J., & Jones, M. B. (2019). *Open data metrics: Lighting the fire*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3525349>
- Ninkov, A., Gregory, K., Peters, I., & Haustein, S. (2021, April 30). Datasets on DataCite – An initial bibliometric investigation. *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference of the International Society for Scientometrics & Informetrics (ISSI 2021)* (pp.837-842), Leuven, Belgium. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730857>
- OECD. (2007). *Revised field of science and technology (FoS) classification in the Frascati manual*. <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>
- Park, H., You, S., & Wolfram, D. (2018). Informal data citation for data sharing and reuse is more common than formal data citation in biomedical fields. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 69(11), 1346–1354. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24049>
- Pepe, A., Goodman, A., Muench, A., Crosas, M., & Erdmann, C. (2014). How do astronomers share data? Reliability and persistence of datasets linked in AAS publications and a qualitative study of data practices among US astronomers. *PLoS ONE*, 9(8), e104798. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0104798>
- Peters, I., Kraker, P., Lex, E., Gumpenberger, C., & Gorraiz, J. (2016). Research data explored: An extended analysis of citations and altmetrics. *Scientometrics*, 107(2), 723–744. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-1887-4>

Robinson-Garcia, N., Jimenez-Contreras, E., & Torres-Salinas, D. (2016). Analyzing data citation practices using the data citation index. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(12), 2964–2975. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23529>

Schmidt, B., Gemeinholzer, B., & Treloar, A. (2016). Open data in global environmental research: The Belmont Forum's open data survey. *PLOS ONE*, 11(1), e0146695. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0146695>

Silvello, G. (2018). Theory and practice of data citation. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 69(1), 6–20. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23917>

Tenopir, C., Rice, N. M., Allard, S., Baird, L., Borycz, J., Christian, L., Grant, B., Olendorf,

R., & Sandusky, R. J. (2020). Data sharing, management, use, and reuse: Practices and perceptions of scientists worldwide. *PLOS ONE*, 15(3), e0229003. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229003>